

FAITH AND CONSUMERISM Negotiating Catholic Commitments in a Materialist Culture

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Abstract: The paper explores how Catholic Clergy and laity negotiate their religious commitments within consumer-driven culture, focusing on the tensions between counter-consumerist teachings and lived practices. Drawing on qualitative research involving interviews and questionnaires with thirty-five Catholic respondents, comprising clergy, religious, seminarians, and laypersons from South India now working in various parts of India, the study investigates how participants reconcile their faith with consumerist behaviours. While most respondents affirm the Church's teachings against materialism, many justify their consumption through moral reasoning grounded in ministry, family, and social values. The findings reveal that instead of wholly rejecting consumerism, Catholic individuals often reinterpret it through ethical frameworks such as altruistic sociality and communal well-being. Such strategic renegotiation of religious values within consumer culture demonstrates that religion, rather than being eclipsed by consumerism, adapts and rearticulates itself in complex and sometimes paradoxical ways. The study contributes to the discourse on lived religion, suggesting that consumerism

may serve both as a challenge to and a vehicle for religious expression in contemporary Catholicism.

Keywords: Consumerism, Materialism, Live Religion, Clergy and Laity, Spiritual Consumerism, Christian Ethics, Religious Adaptation.

INTRODUCTION

Consumerism and materialistic culture in postmodern society have influenced how people perceive what it means to give up and renounce things at the individual or community levels. Despite many religions preaching simple living, economic materialism through a frivolous and selfish collection of products, called consumerism, is spreading, engulfing both rich and poor, cutting across religions. Faithful either accommodate or reject such behavior. We observe the paradox of faith proclamations and the way they are practised. I have known the ordained priests who possess many things and consume out of proportion despite their vow of poverty. Similarly, the laity who are very regular to church activities and sacramental duties have been influenced by consumerism to a large extent. My study, then, seeks to find answers for the following questions or dilemmas: How do the faithful accommodate consumerism in their life despite a robust religious belief against such behaviour? Why do they reconcile their religious precepts with materialism? How do the clergy and the laity, who preach against consumerism and are aware of their religion's vital teachings against consumerism, live their faith with this contradiction? Therefore, I will explore how they reconcile their religious precepts with materialism into consumer culture. I will also study the contradictions between the counter-consumerist opinions and their consumerist practices among the clergy and the laity.

1. RELIGION IN A CONSUMERIST AGE

Consumerism consistently addresses the changing quality of lived religion. The change could be either a complete

rejection or a conducive adaptation. Along with the questions raised earlier, this research could help us know how modern religion is deeply entwined with consumerism norms and practices. We will also understand how consumerism brings disconnection and moves us away from spirituality and religion, pushing us closer to materialism. Further, I explore whether consumerism is a threat to religion, whether it is replacing religion, whether religion is losing customers to consumerism because some people are finding more joy in consumerism than God, and whether consumerism is taking people away from God.

Ann Swidler argues that “People in settled periods can live with the great discontinuity between talk and action.”¹ Inglehart explains that a “high level of existential security is also conducive to the secularization – a systematic erosion of religious practices, values, and beliefs.”² The Catholic clergy are assured of secured life. Their existential security and their settled lives might be one of the factors for the disparity between their talk about anti-materialism and their life of pro-materialism. Numerous researchers suggest that contemporary religions have often embraced consumerism.³ The analysis of consumption patterns in Romania, Turkey, the USA, and Western Europe, illustrates five types of ethics used to justify materialism: romanticism, Protestant utilitarianism, altruistic sociality, generalized sociality, and fairness or equity.⁴ This research will find which of those patterns are operative among the Catholic clergy & laity in India.

¹ Ann Swidler, “Culture in Action: Symbols and Strategies,” *American Sociological Review* 51 (1986): 280.

² Ronald F. Inglehart, *Cultural Evolution: People’s Motivations are Changing and Reshaping the World* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2018), 2.

³ Cf. Simon Coleman, *The Globalisation of Charismatic Christianity: Spreading the Gospel of Prosperity* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2000); David Lyon, *Jesus in Disneyland: Religion in Postmodern Times* (Cambridge: Polity Press, 2000); Vincent Miller, *Consuming Religion: Christian Faith and Practice in a Consumer Culture* (New York: Continuum, 2004); Robert Wuthnow, *God and Mammon in America* (New York: Free press, 1994).

⁴ Cf. Güliz Ger and Russell W. Belk, “Accounting for Materialism in Four Cultures,” *Journal of Material Culture* 4 (1999): 184-204.

Koushiki Choudhury explored how consumers reconcile their religious precepts with materialism in today's consumerist society, with an ethnographic study of one of the world's largest Nichiren Buddhist organizations. He found that religion can transcend the spirit of materialism and the duality of spiritualism in conflict with materialism. Burikova proposed that consumerism is not an aberration from a path to salvation, but it possesses "a utopian potential of its own." Moreover, his study among Slovak Catholic homes established that "in consumption practices related to homes, consumerism merges with religion, and becomes a vehicle for expressing [the faithful's] concern for religious values, particularly for the Christian family."⁵ Similarly, do the Catholic clergy and the laity show the same tendencies of consumerism merging with religion? How do they justify the contradictions in their committed life? This exploration leads us to observe how a lived religion adapts to cultural changes.

3. INVESTIGATING LIVED RELIGION: RESEARCH DESIGN

To respond to the questions posed above, I conducted a semi-structured interview with Catholic clergy and the laity.⁶ The table below provides details about the sample. The sample consists of 35 Catholics: Religious priests (5), Diocesan priests (4), Seminarians (5), religious nuns (7), and laity (6 male and 8 female). A significant section of the group falls under the age group of 31-40 years of age. The sample consists of 40% of the laity and 60% of the clergy/religious/nuns.

⁵ Zuzana Burikova, "Consumerism in Slovak Catholic Homes," in *Religion, Consumerism, and Sustainability: Paradise Lost?*, ed. Lyn Thomas (Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan, 2010), 137-151.

⁶ The participants are predominantly from the southern states of India, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, and Karnataka, with the exception of two from the northeastern states. Although they originate from the South, they are currently serving in diverse locations across India, including Lucknow, Guwahati, Varanasi, Shillong, Patna, Hyderabad, Pune, Mangalore, Jammu and Kashmir, and Delhi.

Age	CLERGY (MALE AND FEMALE)				LAITY		Total	%	
	Priests		Brothers	Nuns	Laity Male	Laity Female			
	Rel.	Dioc.							
20-30	0	0	3	1	3	0	7	20%	
31-40	3	0	2	4	1	5	15	43%	
41-50	2	2		1		1	6	17%	
51<		2		1	2	2	7	20%	
Total	5	4	5	7	6	8	35		
%	21 (60%)				14 (40%)				

I used Google forms to collect responses by administering a questionnaire. The respondents are highly educated. Most of them have completed their post-graduate studies, except for five seminarians in formation who are pursuing their Bachelor in theological studies. It is evident from their educational background that the respondents know both the theological and ecclesial stance against consumerism. By their vowed life, the clergy are more obliged to live a simpler life than the laity do. Despite vital anti-consumerist doctrines, one can observe the affluent living in the clergy. They spend lavishly on decorations, gifts, and community parties during feast days. Anyone who walks into any church will surely see the traces of materialism in their lofty domes, gold-coated tabernacles, etc. Therefore, the contradiction between anti-consumerist opinions and consumerist practices among the Catholic clergy is evident. Most of the laity in my study are very faithful Catholics who actively participate in Church activities such as teaching catechism and volunteering for social outreach programs. Having known their lifestyle, I assume that they also indicate their adherence to consumeristic practices.

At the beginning of the interviews, I briefly explained the purpose of the research. I kept open the time interval for

the interview. However, I informed them that it would take approximately 20 to 30 mins. During the interviews and in the transcripts collected online, I observed that all of them were interested in speaking about the topic. They agreed upon the evil effects of consumerism in both the Church and society. I asked them how they pictured a good Catholic. Then, I asked them how they lived out their faith surrounded by consumeristic culture. The Gospels are the hermeneutical key for Christian living. So, I placed before them some Biblical verses that directly rejected materialistic behavior and asked them how they interpreted them.

4. BETWEEN CREED & CONSUMPTION: PATTERNS OF RELIGIOUS NEGOTIATION

In the analysis, I focused on contradictions between the respondents' counter-consumerist opinions and their consumerist practices. Drawing on the clergy's responses and those of the laity concerning their way of living, I sought answers as to how religious identities and practices merge with and differentiate themselves from consumer identities and practices.⁷ To examine how they relate to consumerism, I analyzed their discourses on consumerism and their knowledge about religious discourses against consumerism. In this paper, I attempt to show how they overcome the contradiction between counter-consumerist discourse and consumerist practice by adhering to Christian values.

When one looks at the transcripts of my interviews, one finds very anti-consumerist tendencies in both clergy and the laity. Several critiques of consumerism reappear in the interviews. Very few of them see consumerism as something that necessarily accompanies progress and is integral to good life. There is a consensus about how the respondents understood the concepts of consumerism and materialism.

⁷ Burikova conducted a similar kind of research concerning household consumption in a Slovak Roman Catholic Village. Cf. Burikova, "Consumerism in Slovak Catholic Homes," 137-151. The survey was confined to only Catholics in a village.

Consumerism is related to ‘consumption of material goods, possession of objects, accumulation of material things, and buying things.’ Consumerism is “having things and not using them.” Therefore, one understands that there is no problem in having things but not using them properly is the issue of consumerism. It is seen as a behavior that leads to the possession of objects more than one needs, collecting things even though one does not need them.

The respondents clearly draw a line between want and need. It is evident that they implicitly indicate that there is potentiality in everyone to live beyond mere desires. It gives an individual, as a respondent expresses, “consuming gets a value of self-worth.” A respondent says that even though it is detrimental to one’s life, one cannot avoid it. Two ways of understanding emerge from the responses: Personal (where one is responsible, one’s needs are priority); impersonal (consumerism, an external factor created by industries). One respondent says, “It is an artificial demand created by industries supported by advertising companies, and that satisfies the modern man even though he does not really need material things.” Another respondent expresses that “consumerism is a system in which the economy is driven by the susceptibility of the consumer to buy.”

Interestingly, only one of them speaks about spiritual consumerism. He says, “There is an excessive consumption of spiritual things too.” Here consumerism is a polarizing factor between material and spiritual aspects of life. It emphasizes or focuses on material aspects of life and denies the spiritual aspects of life.

When discussing how consumerism is a problem for society and the Church, the respondents usually mention consumerism’s evil nature. They see consumerism as a false path to happiness. A respondent says, “Consumerism has led to self-centeredness, self-sufficiency, and selfishness.” It leads to an excessive orientation to the valuation of things over people. They emphasize that the consumption of material things will alienate people from relationships

with other people. A respondent says, “Rich become richer.” Another says, “it leads to egoism, selfishness, social injustice and disregard for charity.” They criticize the fact that people increasingly focus more on hoarding things at the expense of relationships. Most of them draw my attention to the distinction between self-centeredness and other-centeredness. The words such as ‘poor and neighbour’ are also frequently mentioned.

Consumerism is seen as anti-religious. The Church is affected by consumerism. It has become part and parcel of the lives of the members of the Church. It is more prominent in the lives of those who teach that consumerism is bad for society and the Church than the laity. It is considered to be going against the Gospel values and the teaching of Jesus Christ. They see consumerism as an anti-witness to Christ’s teachings. In the Church, “there is the institutionalization of consumeristic ways in the name of faith and devotion.” The laity highlights the worldly life of the priests and religious. The use of gadgets during liturgical celebrations is seen as something wrong and unnecessary. They think that consumerism within the Church might distance the poor from the Church and vice versa.

The Church is trying to imitate the existing cultures in society. A respondent points out, “The Church needs to be careful of being trapped by the consumeristic mindset of the people. The Church should not be like shopping malls and mega-mart.” It is quite surprising to note that if one is faithful to prayer and worship, consumerism is accepted. If one is helping the other, then there is no problem with having more things. It is surprising to note that when asked for any religious discourses, many were silent. However, some of the respondents refer to scriptural passages and the recent teachings of Pope Francis.⁸ The laity recall that they heard about consumerism in sermons.

⁸ The respondents referred to the Biblical verses, such as Lk 12:13-21; Gen 6:1-8; 19:12ff; Mt 5:1-12; Mk 10:23-25; Mt 6:25; 1 Tim 6:17; Mt 6:19-20; Mk 8:36. It was quite surprising to note that most of the clergy could not recall any religious discourses, but the laity was quick to recall.

Despite the negative connotations of consumerism, most of them had unique consumption patterns and aspirations that appear consumerist and highly materialist. Some of the respondents compromise, saying: “We need things as long as they are useful.” Examining consumerism in Western Europe, the US, Turkey, and Romania, Güliz Ger and Russell W. Belk reveal that though materialism is considered to be socially destructive, in all countries, high levels of consumption were taken as constituting the good life, while consumption by particular individuals was morally legitimated by rationality and utility, or altruistic spending for others.⁹

The clergy in my survey justify saying that “as long as it is used to bring forth greater end,” there is no problem to go with the existing culture. Therefore, for the sake of greater ends, one compromises with it. Similarly, for the sake of ministry, apostolate, they need resources. So, a priest says, “I do not see them as contradictions but as a means for religious living.” A nun affirms that “all that we possess should help us to live our commitment.” Another justification is that things are seen as gifts from God and are to be used to better one’s ministry and the community. Peer pressure is one of the prominent justifications of consumerism among the clergy. At the same time, the laity feel that spending during special occasions is justified. A woman says, “In certain instances, weddings, birthdays, it is to celebrate and cheer ourselves. It also brings joy and togetherness in the family.” A man responds, “We need the materials to lead a standard life.” Yet another woman says, “God wants us to be happy and provides out of his generosity and goodness but not at the cost of denying somebody’s right over it.” There is no problem in having more as long as one is ready to share with others. If the purpose of having things is for the community’s mission and wellbeing, and building relationships, then the respondents have no problem with consumerism.

⁹ Ger and Belk, “Accounting for Materialism in Four Cultures,” 184-204.

4.1 Rationalizing the Paradox: Moral Frameworks in Religious Life

In my analysis, I was struck by the apparent inconsistency between respondents' condemnation of consumerism and materialism in voicing their values and criticisms of other people's consumption orientation versus their materialistic behaviours. Such contradictions between anti-materialist and counter-consumerist opinions and consumerist practice are shared. There are various ways in which consumers rationalize their consumption practices to resolve this contradiction and legitimate their consumption as necessary and decent. Analyzing consumption patterns, the analysis shows that the respondents resonate with illustrating five types of ethics used to justify materialism: romanticism (joyous passionate, cultivated aestheticism or passionate sharing and pleasure justifications), Protestant utilitarianism (wants are seen as natural needs), altruistic sociality (spending for others), generalized sociality (being part of a world of progress), and fairness or equity (deservingness).¹⁰ All these accounts suggest that consumption is also a moral project.

I will concentrate on how many respondents manage to live with this contradiction and what kind of morality they use to justify their consumption. Firstly, they consider themselves somehow living with consumerism. Respondents say: "They live with it," "I cannot avoid it." In my interviews, I asked what the life of devoted Catholics should look like. The most usual answer was to live a life according to the Gospel values, share with others, follow the teachings of Jesus Christ, discern between need and want. Thus, the typical remedy according to them is to "associate with the people who are not so fortunate and to share with others from what one has."

Some of the laity see material desires and consumption related to the religious practice of creating a better Christian community. The laity see the celebrations of important

¹⁰ Ger and Belk, "Accounting for Materialism in Four Cultures," 184-204.

moments in their life, such as marriage, birthday as a means of bringing the family together. Whereas the clergy compromise with consumerism in the name of effective ministry, coping with society's trends. One of the religious says, to have the knowledge, they need to have gadgets. I would see a kind of generalized sociality operative among the clergy. For both the Church and the laity, their desire to avoid consumerism, with all their inherent materiality, is an appropriate medium for expressing their care for their families, their ministry, and their faith.

Belk, Ger, and Askegaard write, "Consumers find various ways to moralize their consumption patterns to justify them as being necessary and decent."¹¹ My respondents do not avoid consumption that fits the definition of consumerism, but instead, they attempt to reconstruct its cultural meaning. Shared consumption is considered a means to happiness if and when it contributes to warm and loving relationships with friends and family. Consumerism is seen as steeped in individualism, but to spend money on family, community, and mission is highly praised. Seen as belonging to the sphere of Christian values, the concern for consumption and families' material wellbeing is morally unproblematic. Consumption is tamed by them and for them it does not represent the dangers of consumerism or alienation.

In consumption practices related to families, to others' care, to the development of the Christian community, consumerism merges with religion. It becomes a vehicle for expressing the respondents' concern for religious values, particularly for the Christian community. It is not seen as dangerous and evil consumerism that would be condemned by the Church.

Works by numerous researchers suggest that contemporary religions have often come to embrace consumerism. But my observations show that contemporary Catholicism has come to embrace and employ these perspectives wholeheartedly,

¹¹ Russell W. Belk, Güliz Ger, and Soren Askegaard, "The Fire of Desire: A Multisited Inquiry into Consumer Passion," *Journal of Consumer Research* 30 (2003): 328.

making them part of proper care for the Christian community. Therefore, the clergy spend on celebrations and building churches, families on festivals, without considering their consumption in this context as consumerist. Their religious identities and practices do not differentiate themselves from consumer identities and practices but merge with them.

The conflict of interests to live a life according to the Christian values and maintain an anti-consumeristic lifestyle keeps the Catholics maintain their identity in the community. Smith says in his third proposition while talking about sub-cultural identity, that “religious traditions have always strategically renegotiated their collective identities by continually reformulating the ways their constructed orthodoxies engage the changing socio-cultural environments they confront.”¹² In my research, it is clear that the respondents do not compromise with their orthodoxies. They condemn consumeristic tendencies. They always refer to living a life according to the Gospel values. They renegotiate with trends of consumerism by renegotiating with its Christian values of sharing with others. They suggest to discern the difference between need and want and become effective in the ministry.

The respondents also differentiate lasting happiness and temporary happiness, earthly life and eternal life. Koushiki Choudhury argues, “instead of negating and eradicating desires, including materialistic desire, one can transform and elevate them to achieve a higher state of life – the principle of earthly desires are enlightenment.”¹³ Therefore, we could conclude that religion can embrace even the paradoxical entities of consumerism, materialism, and spiritualism, and transcend thought duality, leading toward a possibility of positive change in society.

¹² Christian Smith, “Toward a ‘Subcultural Identity’ Theory of Religious Strength,” in *American Evangelicalism: Embattled and Thriving* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1989), 97.

¹³ Koushiki Choudhury, “Materialism, Consumerism, and Religion: A Buddhist Vision for Nonprofit Marketing,” *International Journal of Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Marketing* 24/6 (2019): 7.

CONCLUSION

I began my research with the assumption that both the clergy and laity have adapted themselves to the culture of consumerism. They also differ in their ways of dealing with the culture of consumerism. As we have seen, interestingly, my assumption was corrected. As Smith pointed out, they only renegotiated with it. He correctly argued that “most people live their lives negotiating the demands of multiple religious and non-religious moral orders - compromising here, synthesizing there, compartmentalizing elsewhere. In such a situation, religion can exert a significant, though not total, influence in human life.”¹⁴ The study shows that consumerism has not deteriorated the commitment of clergy and the laity to their religious teachings and practices. It instead alerts them to be careful about differentiating their wants and needs. It commits them to the Gospel values. After renegotiating with consumerism, religion does not lose its essence; instead brings out the importance of practising religious values such as caring for the other and nature.

We may also think of consumerism along more optimistic lines by not understanding it as an aberration from a path to salvation but rather as possessing a utopian potential of its own. The divide between the sacred and profane, religious and secular, is also blurred. In short, religion is pressed away from traditional hierarchies, doctrines, and rituals, and transformed into the possible lifestyle of choices. A crucial task for further research is to understand the pros and cons of such changes. It could be further studied to see how consumerism can be a culture of open horizons, a culture of open possibilities for all religions. Further research can also explore the concepts of self-enhancement and self-transcendence in the context of the world’s various beliefs and materialistic values and possible implications for social welfare.

¹⁴ Smith, “Toward a ‘Subcultural Identity’ Theory of Religious Strength,” 106.